

A PROMISING METHOD FOR POST-COVID/LONG-COVID SYNDROME: NONINVASIVE VAGUS NERVE STIMULATION

Ali Veysel ÖZDEN

Department of Physiotherapy and Rehabilitation, Bahçeşehir University, Istanbul,
Turkey.

Alper PERÇİN

Department of Physiotherapy and Rehabilitation, Iğdır University, Iğdır, Turkey

INTRODUCTION

The SARS-CoV-2 (COVID-19) pandemic has caused unprecedented morbidity, mortality and global disruption. Post-acute COVID (known colloquially as long COVID) refers to persistent symptoms 3 weeks after COVID-19 infection, while 'Chronic COVID' describes symptoms lasting more than 12 weeks (1). Autonomic symptoms of acute infection are common and are being described with increasing frequency. While most patients have mild symptoms and recover within several weeks, more than 50% are left with ongoing symptoms several months later many of which appear autonomic in nature (2). Disorders affecting the central or peripheral autonomic pathways, or both, can manifest with autonomic failure (including orthostatic hypotension, anhidrosis, impaired reaction to light, dry mouth, dry eyes, gastrointestinal dysmotility, neurogenic bladder, erectile dysfunction) or autonomic hyperactivity (primary hypertension, tachycardia, hyperhidrosis) (3). In autonomic dysfunction, there is a deterioration in the balance between the sympathetic and parasympathetic systems, which creates a load on the body (4). Pre-existing sympathetic hyperactivity may increase the morbidity and mortality of COVID-19 infection, but the disease itself may impair autonomic nervous system (ANS) function due to emotional stress, hypoxia, etc. The disease progresses more severely in people with significant autonomic dysfunction before COVID-19. Autonomic dysfunction, measured with heart rate variability (HRV), is more pronounced in patients with more disease severity during the active infection period (e.g. O₂ saturation \leq 93%, lung infiltration $>$ 50%). In those whose autonomic dysfunction persists, the course of the disease is worse and autonomic dysfunction is more common in the 3 months follow-up after discharge. Post COVID autonomic dysfunction rate is higher in patients with pre-disease autonomic dysfunction (5,6).

In the observational study of Stella et al, the incidence of autonomic dysfunction after symptomatic COVID-19 infection is $\frac{1}{4}$ at 9 months follow-up and more common in women (7). Several investigators have reported dysautonomia persisting for nearly a year following initial infection. Hyperactivity states such as tachycardia (tonic activity) and postural orthostatic tachycardia syndrome (POTS)(phasic activity) are more common than autonomic insufficiency states such as hypotension (tonic activity) and orthostatic hypotension (phasic activity) (8,9). In fact, the above-mentioned hyperactivity states may be due to parasympathetic hypoactivity (sympathetic activity may not be altered), so it can be stated that it is somehow written according to end-organ responses. As Berntson et al declared, hypotension may have developed because of parasympathetic hyperactivity (4). In their retrospective study, Shouman et al mentioned that orthostatic intolerance without significant hemodynamic changes is the most common finding in autonomic dysfunction after COVID-19 infection (10).

ANS Dysfunction

An autonomic dysfunction can be expected during the COVID-19 infection to fight or flight, as in other symptomatic infections. Acute, coordinated alterations in homeostatic settings (allostasis) can be crucial for surviving stressors such as infectious diseases and sepsis however, autonomic dysfunction in chronically decreased homeostatic efficiencies (dyshomeostasis) may cause debilitating or lethal vicious cycles (11). Sympathetic hyperactivation is an important component of autonomic dysregulation in infections and is associated with hyperinflammatory states (12). It can be stated that the dysfunctional state in the ANS activity (increased sympathetic activity, suppressed parasympathetic activity) contributes to morbidity and mortality in COVID-19 patients, and the solution of this problem can be a goal in treatment. In animal studies, surgical vagotomy increases alveolar damage due to overproduction of inflammatory cytokines such as IL-6 (13). Electrical or pharmacological vagal nerve activation attenuates lung injury by modulating the inflammatory response and tissue damage (14). In rat models of sepsis, vagus nerve stimulation (VNS) has been shown to reduce the release of proinflammatory cytokines, prevent hypotension, regulate coagulation, inhibit fibrinolysis activation, reduce organ dysfunction, and increase survival (15).

Many underlying mechanisms have been proposed for post covid/long covid autonomic dysfunction; direct invasion of the ANS by the COVID-19 (autonom neuropathy),

autoimmunity disorder against ANS, prolonged bed rest, microangiopathy, secondary to another pathology such as covid-induced stroke or encephalitis, both psychological and physiological stress caused by the disease itself (in adaptive, compensatory context) (2,16). New-onset POTS and other autonomic disorders can follow COVID-19 in previously healthy non-hospitalized patients who experience persistent neurologic and cardiovascular symptoms after resolution of acute infection (17-21). Orthostatic hypotension with recurrent falls, tachycardia, chronic fatigue, brain fog, muscle soreness, anxiety, irritable bowel syndrome can be seen in post covid/long covid (1,22). Inflammatory demyelinating polyneuropathies, transverse myelitis characterized by autonomic dysfunction after COVID-19 have also been reported in the literature (23,24). Heart rate and blood pressure instability, pupillary dysfunction, urinary retention, dizziness, orthostatic intolerance may accompany COVID-19 related Guillain-Barré syndrome (25).

Larsen et al define orthostatic intolerance, palpitations/tachycardia, temperature intolerance, labile blood pressure, new-onset hypertension, gastrointestinal symptoms (e.g., abdominal pain, bloating, nausea) as symptoms suggestive of autonomic dysfunction. However, fatigue, headache, cognitive impairment (brain fog) were not associated with autonomic dysfunction in the study (2). Similarly, Townsend et al, in their evaluation of post-covid patients with and without chronic fatigue, stated that fatigue was not associated with autonomic dysfunction but was associated with anxiety. They applied heart rate variability (HRV), 24-hour blood pressure monitoring, prefrontal cortex oxygenation with infrared spectroscopy to evaluate ANS activity (26). Lo argue that COVID-19 related chronic fatigue may be due to hypotension but Barizien and colleagues directly linked fatigue to autonomic dysfunction in long COVID-19 patients (27,28). In fact, fatigue may accompany conditions with autonomic dysfunction such as bradycardia or tachycardia, in which hypoactivity or hyperactivity of the branches of the ANS can be seen (21).

Neuromodulation and VNS

Neuromodulation methods can improve and regulate the activities of the sympathetic and parasympathetic branches. VNS is approved for the treatment of drug refractory epilepsy and depression. Also it has been shown to attenuate hyperinflammation and it carries the potential for correction of the imbalance in ANS. So it can be said that noninvasive VNS can be used as an adjunct therapy in COVID-19 patients (29). In COVID-19 viral pneumonia cases transcutaneous auricular VNS can reduce markedly elevated interleukin-6 levels (30). In

addition, VNS appears to be useful in COVID-19 related respiratory symptoms (31). However, selective VNS is important to decrease unwanted side effects like bronchoconstriction in COVID-19 caused acute respiratory distress syndrome. VNS can further decrease airway passage by increasing mucus secretion. To prevent this, organ/function-specific stimulation will be better for regulation of the ANS (32). VNS is also recommended for the treatment of cytokine storm in severe COVID-19 patients and again monitoring of the ANS is suggested for more accurate treatment (33,34). Cytokine storm is strongly correlated with sympathetic overactivity and ANS dysfunction. So it can be said that PNS-mediated anti-inflammatory effect is diminished in hyperinflammatory status. Chronic ANS dysfunction in post-COVID patients probably continues in a vicious circle. Disease-related stress also aggravates the condition (35). As a safe treatment method, auricular VNS can be preferred as an adjuvant therapy in Covid-19 and similar infectious diseases with hyperinflammation (36). The ability of VNS to modulate the immune system without impairing specific immunity to infectious agents is highly advantageous in the treatment of inflammatory conditions due to COVID-19 and other infectious agents.

Non-invasive neuromodulation methods can be preferred for the management of COVID-19 symptoms both in the active disease period or after it to control long COVID (37). Non-invasive cranial microcurrent stimulation can reduce vascular dysregulation and improve visual/cognitive impairment in long COVID patients (38). VNS can be accepted as a cranial neurostimulation and moreover it can regulate the ANS dysfunction. Vagus nerve signal disorder and ANS dysfunction are most likely to occur in long COVID. This is often accompanied by an immune system disorder. Fatigue, malaise, brain fog, headaches, sleep problems, muscle pain, tachycardia are commonly seen in long COVID and all are related with ANS dysfunction (39). VNS is a method that has been recognized as safe and it can be beneficial for the treatment of postural orthostatic tachycardia syndrome and other symptoms related with long COVID (40).

Conclusion

The COVID-19 pandemic has had devastating health and socioeconomic impacts on people. Although the effects of the disease decreased with the use of vaccines, some people who had the disease continued to experience symptoms such as fatigue, brain fog, and tachycardia that impair their quality of life. Post-COVID/Long-COVID seems likely to occur as the virus itself or the clinical condition it causes affects the ANS. Noninvasive VNS may be an additional treatment option to control symptoms seen in Post-COVID/Long-COVID.

The applications so far in different indications show that noninvasive VNS is an effective and safe treatment method.

Acknowledgements

None. No funding to declare.

Authors' Contributions

A.V.Ö.: provided the conception and design of the study, revised it critically for important intellectual content; A.P.: provided the revised the article critically for important intellectual content and gave final approval of the version to be submitted.

Conflict of Interest

All authors have no conflict of interest to report.

Financial Support

This research received no specific grant from any funding agency in the public, commercial, or not for profit sectors.

REFERENCES

1. Dani M, Dirksen A, Taraborrelli P, Torocastro M, Panagopoulos D, Sutton R, Lim PB. Autonomic dysfunction in 'long COVID': rationale, physiology and management strategies. *Clin Med (Lond)*. 2021 Jan;21(1):e63-e67.
2. Larsen NW, Stiles LE, Miglis MG. Preparing for the long-haul: Autonomic complications of COVID-19. *Auton Neurosci*. 2021 Nov;235:102841.
3. Benarroch EE. Physiology and Pathophysiology of the Autonomic Nervous System. *Continuum (Minneap Minn)*. 2020 Feb;26(1):12-24.
4. Berntson GG, Cacioppo JT, Quigley KS. Autonomic determinism: the modes of autonomic control, the doctrine of autonomic space, and the laws of autonomic constraint. *Psychol Rev*. 1991 Oct;98(4):459-87.
5. Porzionato A, Emmi A, Barbon S, Boscolo-Berto R, Stecco C, Stocco E, Macchi V, De Caro R. Sympathetic activation: a potential link between comorbidities and COVID-19. *FEBS J*. 2020 Sep;287(17):3681-3688.
6. Pan Y, Yu Z, Yuan Y, Han J, Wang Z, Chen H, Wang S, Wang Z, Hu H, Zhou L, Lai Y, Zhou Z, Wang Y, Meng G, Yu L and Jiang H. Alteration of Autonomic Nervous System Is Associated With Severity and Outcomes in Patients With COVID-19. *Front. Physiol.* (2021) 12:630038.

7. Buoite Stella A, Furlanis G, Frezza NA, Valentinotti R, Ajcevic M, Manganotti P. Autonomic dysfunction in post-COVID patients with and without neurological symptoms: a prospective multidomain observational study. *J Neurol*. 2021 Aug 12;1-10.
8. Becker RC. Autonomic dysfunction in SARS-COV-2 infection acute and long-term implications COVID-19 editor's page series. *J Thromb Thrombolysis*. 2021 Oct;52(3):692-707.
9. Gibbins I. Functional organization of autonomic neural pathways. *Organogenesis*. 2013 Jul-Sep;9(3):169-75.
10. Shouman K, Vanichkachorn G, Cheshire WP, Suarez MD, Shelly S, Lamotte GJ, Sandroni P, Benarroch EE, Berini SE, Cutsforth-Gregory JK, Coon EA, Mauermann ML, Low PA, Singer W. Autonomic dysfunction following COVID-19 infection: an early experience. *Clin Auton Res*. 2021 Jun;31(3):385-394.
11. Goldstein DS. The extended autonomic system, dyshomeostasis, and COVID-19. *Clin Auton Res*. 2020 Aug;30(4):299-315.
12. Fudim M, Qadri YJ, Ghadimi K, MacLeod DB, Molinger J, Piccini JP, Whittle J, Wischmeyer PE, Patel MR, Ulloa L. Implications for Neuromodulation Therapy to Control Inflammation and Related Organ Dysfunction in COVID-19. *J Cardiovasc Transl Res*. 2020 Dec;13(6):894-899.
13. dos Santos CC, Shan Y, Akram A, Slutsky AS, Haitzma JJ. Neuroimmune regulation of ventilator-induced lung injury. *Am J Respir Crit Care Med*. 2011 Feb 15;183(4):471-82.
14. van Westerloo DJ, Giebelen IA, Meijers JC, Daalhuisen J, de Vos AF, Levi M, van der Poll T. Vagus nerve stimulation inhibits activation of coagulation and fibrinolysis during endotoxemia in rats. *J Thromb Haemost*. 2006 Sep;4(9):1997-2002.
15. Huston JM, Gallowitsch-Puerta M, Ochani M, Ochani K, Yuan R, Rosas-Ballina M, Ashok M, Goldstein RS, Chavan S, Pavlov VA, Metz CN, Yang H, Czura CJ, Wang H, Tracey KJ. Transcutaneous vagus nerve stimulation reduces serum high mobility group 1 levels and improves survival in murine sepsis. *Crit Care Med*. 2007 Dec;35(12):2762-8.
16. Davido B, Seang S, Tubiana R, de Truchis P. Post-COVID-19 chronic symptoms: a postinfectious entity? *Clin Microbiol Infect*. 2020 Nov;26(11):1448-1449.
17. Blitshteyn S, Whitelaw S. Postural orthostatic tachycardia syndrome (POTS) and other autonomic disorders after COVID-19 infection: a case series of 20 patients. *Immunol Res*. 2021 Apr;69(2):205-211.
18. O'Sullivan JS, Lyne A, Vaughan CJ. COVID-19-induced postural orthostatic tachycardia syndrome treated with ivabradine. *BMJ Case Rep*. 2021 Jun 14;14(6):e243585.
19. Miglis MG, Prieto T, Shaik R, Muppidi S, Sinn DI, Jaradeh S. A case report of postural tachycardia syndrome after COVID-19. *Clin Auton Res*. 2020 Oct;30(5):449-451.
20. Raj SR, Arnold AC, Barboi A, Claydon VE, Limberg JK, Lucci VM, Numan M, Peltier A, Snapper H, Vernino S; American Autonomic Society. Long-COVID postural tachycardia syndrome: an American Autonomic Society statement. *Clin Auton Res*. 2021 Jun;31(3):365-368.

21. Johansson M, Ståhlberg M, Runold M, Nygren-Bonnier M, Nilsson J, Olshansky B, Bruchfeld J, Fedorowski A. Long-Haul Post-COVID-19 Symptoms Presenting as a Variant of Postural Orthostatic Tachycardia Syndrome: The Swedish Experience. *JACC Case Rep.* 2021 Apr;3(4):573-580.
22. Suresh K, Alam MDU, Satkovich E. COVID-19-Associated Dysautonomia. *Cureus.* 2021 Aug 13;13(8):e17156.
23. Kakumoto T, Kobayashi S, Yuuki H, Kainaga M, Shiota Y, Hamada M, Hashimoto Maeda M, Kubota A, Kawai M, Saito M, Ishiura H, Toda T. Cranial Nerve Involvement and Dysautonomia in Post-COVID-19 Guillain-Barre Syndrome. *Intern Med.* 2021 Nov 1;60(21):3477-3480.
24. Moreno-Escobar MC, Kataria S, Khan E, Subedi R, Tandon M, Peshwe K, Kramer J, Niaze F, Sriwastava S. Acute transverse myelitis with Dysautonomia following SARS-CoV-2 infection: A case report and review of literature. *J Neuroimmunol.* 2021 Apr 15;353:577523.
25. Biassoni E, Assini A, Gandoglia I, Benedetti L, Boni S, Pontali E, Feasi M, Gandolfo F, Del Sette M. The importance of thinking about Guillain-Barre syndrome during the COVID-19 pandemic: a case with pure dysautonomic presentation. *J Neurovirol.* 2021 Aug;27(4):662-665.
26. Townsend L, Moloney D, Finucane C, McCarthy K, Bergin C, Bannan C, et al. (2021) Fatigue following COVID-19 infection is not associated with autonomic dysfunction. *PLoS ONE* 16(2): e0247280.
27. Lo YL. COVID-19, fatigue, and dysautonomia. *J Med Virol.* 2021 Mar;93(3):1213.
28. Barizien N, Le Guen M, Russel S, Touche P, Huang F, Vallée A. Clinical characterization of dysautonomia in long COVID-19 patients. *Sci Rep.* 2021 Jul 7;11(1):14042.
29. Azabou E, Bao G, Bounab R, Heming N, Annane D. Vagus Nerve Stimulation: A Potential Adjunct Therapy for COVID-19. *Front Med (Lausanne).* 2021 May 7;8:625836.
30. Boezaart AP, Botha DA. Treatment of Stage 3 COVID-19 With Transcutaneous Auricular Vagus Nerve Stimulation Drastically Reduces Interleukin-6 Blood Levels: A Report on Two Cases. *Neuromodulation.* 2021 Jan;24(1):166-167.
31. Staats P, Giannakopoulos G, Blake J, Liebler E, Levy RM. The Use of Non-invasive Vagus Nerve Stimulation to Treat Respiratory Symptoms Associated With COVID-19: A Theoretical Hypothesis and Early Clinical Experience. *Neuromodulation.* 2020 Aug;23(6):784-788.
32. Mastitskaya S, Thompson N, Holder D. Selective Vagus Nerve Stimulation as a Therapeutic Approach for the Treatment of ARDS: A Rationale for Neuro-Immunomodulation in COVID-19 Disease. *Front Neurosci.* 2021 Apr 13;15:667036.
33. Bonaz B, Sinniger V, Pellissier S. Targeting the cholinergic anti-inflammatory pathway with vagus nerve stimulation in patients with Covid-19? *Bioelectron Med.* 2020 Jul 29;6:15.

34. Qin Z, Xiang K, Su DF, Sun Y, Liu X. Activation of the Cholinergic Anti-Inflammatory Pathway as a Novel Therapeutic Strategy for COVID-19. *Front Immunol*. 2021 Feb 8;11:595342.
35. Al-Kuraishy HM, Al-Gareeb AI, Qusti S, Alshammari EM, Gyebi GA, Batiha GE. Covid-19-Induced Dysautonomia: A Menace of Sympathetic Storm. *ASN Neuro*. 2021 Jan-Dec;13:17590914211057635.
36. Kaniusas E, Szeles JC, Kampusch S, Alfageme-Lopez N, Yucuma-Conde D, Li X, Mayol J, Neumayer C, Papa M, Panetsos F. Non-invasive Auricular Vagus Nerve Stimulation as a Potential Treatment for Covid19-Originated Acute Respiratory Distress Syndrome. *Front Physiol*. 2020 Jul 28;11:890.
37. Baptista AF, Baltar A, Okano AH, Moreira A, Campos ACP, Fernandes AM, Brunoni AR, Badran BW, Tanaka C, de Andrade DC, da Silva Machado DG, Morya E, Trujillo E, Swami JK, Camprodon JA, Monte-Silva K, Sá KN, Nunes I, Goulardins JB, Bikson M, Sudbrack-Oliveira P, de Carvalho P, Duarte-Moreira RJ, Pagano RL, Shinjo SK, Zana Y. Applications of Non-invasive Neuromodulation for the Management of Disorders Related to COVID-19. *Front Neurol*. 2020 Nov 25;11:573718.
38. Sabel BA, Zhou W, Huber F, Schmidt F, Sabel K, Gonschorek A, Bilc M. Non-invasive brain microcurrent stimulation therapy of long-COVID-19 reduces vascular dysregulation and improves visual and cognitive impairment. *Restor Neurol Neurosci*. 2021;39(6):393-408.
39. Proal AD, VanElzakker MB. Long COVID or Post-acute Sequelae of COVID-19 (PASC): An Overview of Biological Factors That May Contribute to Persistent Symptoms. *Front Microbiol*. 2021 Jun 23;12:698169.
40. Petelin Gadze Z, Bujan Kovac A, Adamec I, Milekic N, Sulentic V. Vagal nerve stimulation is beneficial in postural orthostatic tachycardia syndrome and epilepsy. *Seizure*. 2018 Apr;57:11-13.